

PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL- PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS BASED ON THE 4K MODEL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21103463>

Abstract. *This article discusses the issues of developing professional and pedagogical competence of future primary school teachers based on the 4K model (creativity, critical thinking, communication and cooperation). The study analyzes the role of the 4K model in the pedagogical education process, its importance in the professional preparation of future teachers, innovative activity and the formation of competencies that meet the requirements of modern education. Also, the methodological possibilities and effectiveness of introducing the 4K model into educational practice are substantiated.*

Keywords: *4K model, professional and pedagogical competence, future teacher, primary education, creativity, critical thinking, communication, cooperation, competency-based approach, pedagogical activity.*

The radical changes taking place in the global education system are placing new demands on the process of training teachers. The rapid development of information and communication technologies, the digitalization of education, new needs emerging in the labor market, and increasing demands for the quality of education require the development of professional and pedagogical competence of future teachers based on modern approaches. In particular, teachers working in the primary education system should be formed as specialists who not only have a thorough knowledge of the basics of science, but also have the ability to think creatively, analyze problems, communicate effectively, and work in a team.

Today, the 4K model (creativity, critical thinking, communication and collaboration), recognized as the skills of the 21st century in international educational practice, is becoming an important component of the educational process. This model serves to develop universal competencies that modern society requires in students and future teachers. In particular, creativity allows you to create new ideas and develop innovative solutions, while critical thinking helps you analyze, evaluate information and draw well-founded conclusions. Communicativeness ensures the organization of effective communication, and collaboration forms the skills of successful work in collective activities.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, large-scale reforms are being implemented to modernize the education system, improve the quality of teacher training, and bring it into line with international standards. In this process, the development of professional and pedagogical competence of future primary school teachers is considered one of the priority tasks. Because the primary education stage serves as the foundation for students' further educational activities, and the professional skills of teachers working at this stage are considered one of the important factors determining the effectiveness of education.

Pedagogical competence is an integrative complex of a teacher's professional knowledge, practical skills, personal qualities and the ability to effectively organize pedagogical activity. From this point of view, using the capabilities of the 4K model serves to consistently develop the components of professional and pedagogical competence in future primary school teachers. This approach increases the professional adaptability of future teachers, prepares them for innovative activities, and expands their opportunities for effectively resolving various pedagogical situations that arise in the educational process.

In the modern education system, the issue of developing the professional and pedagogical competence of a teacher is of particular importance. In particular, in the process of training primary school teachers, it is important not only to acquire theoretical knowledge, but also to form competencies that allow them to be effectively used in practical activities. In this regard, the 4K model is recognized as one of the effective means of developing the professional and pedagogical competence of future primary school teachers .

Professional-pedagogical competence is an integrated system of knowledge, skills, qualifications and personal qualities necessary for the successful implementation of pedagogical activity by a teacher. This competence includes methodological, communicative, social, information-communication and reflexive competencies. The development of these competencies in future primary school teachers is considered an important factor in increasing the quality and effectiveness of education.

The first component of the 4K model is *creativity* , which develops the ability of future teachers to think in new ways, put forward innovative ideas, and apply a creative approach to the educational process. A teacher with creative thinking organizes lessons taking into account the interests of students, creates problem situations, and enriches the content of education with modern pedagogical technologies. The development of creativity in primary education serves to increase students' motivation for knowledge and effectively organize the educational process.

The second component of the 4K model is *critical thinking* . Critical thinking demonstrates the teacher's ability to analyze, compare, evaluate information, and make informed decisions. Future primary school teachers need to be able to deeply analyze pedagogical situations and choose effective methods, taking into account the individual characteristics of students. The development of critical thinking skills creates the opportunity to solve problems encountered in pedagogical activity on a scientific basis.

The third component of the 4K model is *communication* , which includes the skills of effective communication, clear and fluent expression of thoughts, listening skills, and establishing pedagogical cooperation. A primary school teacher regularly communicates with students, parents, and colleagues. Therefore, the development of communicative competence is one of the important factors ensuring the effectiveness of pedagogical activity. A teacher with a communication culture can create a healthy psychological environment, increase the activity of students in the educational process, and achieve effective results in achieving educational goals.

The fourth component of the 4K model is *collaboration* , which forms the skills of teamwork, mutual exchange of ideas, sharing of responsibilities and joint action towards a common goal. Today, the educational process is based on the mutual cooperation of many subjects. Therefore, the development of collaboration competence in future teachers is an important pedagogical task. The educational process organized on the basis of collaboration increases the independent thinking, social activity and professional adaptability of students.

In developing the professional and pedagogical competence of future primary school teachers based on the 4K model, it is also important to properly organize students' independent educational activities. In the process of independent education, students study various pedagogical problems, conduct research on their solutions, and try to express their opinions on a scientific basis. This serves to develop their creative thinking, critical analysis, and independent decision-making skills. Effective organization of independent education forms the competencies of future teachers to work on themselves, strive for professional development, and learn throughout their lives.

The use of project activities in the training of future primary school teachers is also a practical expression of the 4K model. In the process of working on a project, students identify a specific pedagogical problem, collect information, analyze it, and present the final result. In this process, creativity plays a role in proposing new ideas, critical thinking in sorting and evaluating information, communication in presenting results, and cooperation in working effectively with group members. As a result, students have an expanded opportunity to connect theoretical knowledge with practical activities.

In today's digital learning environment, the use of modern information and communication technologies is of particular importance for implementing the 4K model. Electronic learning platforms, virtual laboratories, online communication tools and interactive educational resources ensure the active participation of students. With the help of such tools, students actively participate in the processes of searching, analyzing, processing and presenting information. This, along with the development of their professional and pedagogical competence, also contributes to the formation of digital competencies.

The analysis shows that the educational process organized on the basis of the 4K model is more effective than traditional teaching methods. Because this model ensures that the student becomes an active participant in the educational process, not a passive listener. The ability of students to freely express their opinions, participate in discussions on problems, work in teams, and develop innovative solutions has a positive impact on their professional development.

The 4K model also serves to develop reflective activity in future teachers. Reflection allows the teacher to analyze his/her own activities, evaluate the results achieved, and identify ways to improve his/her future activities. A teacher working on the basis of a reflective approach is able to identify the achievements and shortcomings in his/her professional activities and strives to constantly work on himself/herself. This ensures the continuous development of pedagogical skills.

Thus, the 4K model is of great theoretical and practical importance in the development of professional and pedagogical competence of future primary school teachers. The educational process organized on the basis of this model serves to in-depth mastery of pedagogical knowledge, the formation of professional skills, preparation for innovative activities, and the training of competitive specialists who can effectively operate in a modern educational environment. Therefore, the widespread use of the possibilities of the 4K model in pedagogical higher education institutions is considered one of the important factors in further improving the professional training of future primary school teachers.

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